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STREAMING FLUENCY: A CORRELATIONAL STUDY BETWEEN VIDEO CONSUMPTION AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract

This study aimed to examine the relationship between the consumption of educational videos and the learning of English language. It was grounded in the theoretical frameworks of Stephen Krashen's Input Hypothesis, which emphasizes the importance of comprehensible input in language learning, and Noam Chomsky's theory of Universal Grammar, which highlights innate linguistic capabilities.

Findings showed that results were very high in terms of vocabulary acquisition and high impact in other areas. Age did not demonstrate any significant correlation to the learning outcome, whereas sex was significantly correlated to pronunciation gain and motivation. The perception of frequency had a positive relationship with acquisition of vocabulary, but a negative association with pronunciation, comprehension of language contexts and listening comprehension when the viewing hours were excessive. While previous studies demonstrated the positive impact of video consumption on vocabulary, pronunciation, and motivation, there is still a lack of knowledge on how structured versus non-structured viewing patterns specifically impact the overall effectiveness of second language acquisition for college students. Findings indicate that directed, systematic and intense exposures to videos work compared to the long hours of unstructured viewing. It is suggested to implement an intervention program, where the curated interactive and time managed video-based activities could be used as a part of language teaching- learning activities to maximize the effects on it.

Keywords: *video consumption, second language acquisition, vocabulary development, pronunciation improvement, language learning motivation*

INTRODUCTION

Video consumption refers to the act of watching video content across various digital platforms and channels. In digital marketing, it is often used to measure the overall performance of promotional video materials. Language acquisition, on the other hand, is the process by which humans develop the ability to understand and produce language.

According to Krashen's Input Hypothesis (1982), comprehensible input—language that learners can understand but is slightly above their current level—is crucial for language development. Videos naturally offer this input through real-life dialogues, visual context, body language, and pronunciation, which help learners grasp meaning beyond just vocabulary or grammar.

Recent studies justify the idea that the use of a video can have a positive effect on language learning. According to Zhang, Li, and Zhou (2023), video content on the social sphere supplements

the vocabulary acquisition and contextual analysis of cultural clues and conversation dynamics, which means that learning is not only cognitively accessible but highly motivating. To further explain this, Gowenlock, Norbury, and Rodd (2024) reported that video-based exposure that is developed through interaction of characters and context creates the responsive listening talents and the skill to acquire the meaning through intonation and verbal terms in kids.

The study of Prabaningtyas and Wulandari (2023) pointed out the effectiveness of YouTube to language vocabulary enlargement where variable, unrehearsed English speech-maintained interest and promoted spontaneous language use, and Sahayu and Friyanto (2019) discovered that the regular watching of the native speakers among those who already learnt the language enhanced pronunciation, familiarity with the accent, and fluent articulation. The study of De Matta et al. (2023) revealed that instructional TikTok videos set in real-life contexts increased the understanding of expressions, knowledge of grammar, and making fewer pronunciation errors among elementary learners due to repetition and imitation, whereas Alvarez et al. (2024) found that Grade 10 students who use Tik Tok English resources are better at using vocabulary, conducting tests on grammatical issues, and fluency in speech.

On the other hand, the study of Golovchun, A. A., et al, (2025) argues that the consumption of video has evolved, and this development has presented additional opportunities of language learners to access authentic content. This study examined the relationship between English language learning and video consumption of BSED second-year English students of Abuyog Community College as the study would fill the existing gap in the research and serve as an indicator of successful teaching methods.

Learning about the relationship of video consumption and second language learning will enable an educator to guide his/her student to become fluent in the language. The study will also be able to present the insights concerning best opportunities students have to utilize video content and educators gain as the important source of language learning.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to explore the correlates, benefits, and potential challenges of video-based learning in the context of second language learning among English major students. It seeks to provide insights that will inform more effective language teaching strategies by examining how video consumption influences learning outcomes. Specifically, this study addresses the following research questions to better understand the advantages and limitations of integrating video materials into language pedagogy.

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Number of hours spent in watching educational video
 - 1.4 Frequency of watching educational videos
2. What is the impact of video consumption on second language learning of BSED second-year English students?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the impact of video consumption and the profile of BSED second-year English students in terms of:
 - 3.1 Age
 - 3.2 Sex
 - 3.3 Number of hours spent in watching educational videos
 - 3.4 Frequency of watching educational videos
4. What intervention program could be recommended based on the results?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to determine the relationship between video consumption and English language learning. The descriptive method was utilized to collect measurable data and describe the conditions of the students' language learning experiences through video content.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were 30 BEd-English students presently enrolled at Abuyog Community College. They were selected using purposive sampling to identify those individuals who had regular accessibility to video materials, and it formed part of their daily language exposure. The sample was appropriate given that it helped to give relevant insight.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted at Abuyog Community College, situated in Abuyog, Leyte, Philippines. The institution was selected primarily due to its proximity to the researchers, who are currently enrolled in the same course, making data collection more practical and efficient. Additionally, the choice was influenced by economic considerations, ensuring that the study could be carried out with accessible resources.

Research Instruments

The primary research instrument was a researcher-made survey questionnaire, which was validated by experts in the field of language education and research. The researchers' consultation with the research adviser and research instructor was conducted to ensure the reliability and validity of the research instrument. Moreover, the questionnaire consisted of two main parts: (i) Profile of the respondents and the frequency and duration of their video consumption. (ii) A set of statements using a Likert scale to measure the perceived impact of video consumption on specific areas of language acquisition, including vocabulary development, grammatical awareness, pronunciation, and comprehension skills.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the actual data collection, permission to distribute the questionnaire was sought from the college president. Researchers are using a quantitative method to collect data. The survey questionnaire was a structured questionnaire that was used as a research instrument. Similarly, the instrument was validated by the experts to establish its content validity and operational suitability to the objectives of the study.

After validation, the revised questionnaire was distributed to the target respondents who met inclusion criteria that the researchers identified. Data were collected by administering and collecting the survey forms, and the responses were coded, tabulated, and statistically analyzed. The confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were kept in the process.

Ethical Consideration

The researchers made sure that the participants sign informed consent before proceeding to answer the questionnaire. The anonymity of any response was kept and the respondents did not reveal any personal identifiers. It was voluntary, and respondents were free to withdraw any time

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during data collection. Confidentiality and anonymity were closely monitored, and all personal information were treated safely consistent with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 but exclusively used per academic research.

Method of Scoring and Interpretation

A. Respondents Profile

Sex	Code	
Male	1	
Female	2	
Age. Gershkoff-Stowe & Rakison (2005)		
Age	Code	Qualitative Description
19-23	1	Emerging Adulthood
24-28	2	Early Adulthood
29-33	3	Established Young Adulthood
34-38	4	Early Middle Adulthood
Numbers of Hours in Spending Educational Video		
1-3 hours	1	
4-6 hours	2	
7-10 hours	3	
Frequency		
Less than a week	1	
3-4 times a week	2	
Daily	3	
Rarely/Never	4	

B. Likert Scale

- 5 – Strongly Agree
- 4 – Agree
- 3 - Neutral
- 2– Disagree
- 1– Strongly Disagree

C. Mean Scores Interpretation

:	Scale	Qualitative Description
	4.20 – 5.00	Very High Impact
	3.40 – 4.19	High Impact
	2.60 – 3.39	Moderate Impact
	1.80 – 2.59	Low Impact
	1.0 – 1.79	Very Low Impact

D. Curriculum Interpretation Guide on Correlation (Pearson, 1895)

Range	Verbal Interpretation
± 1.00	Perfect Correlation
$\pm 0.76 - \pm 0.99$	Very high positive/negative correlation
$\pm 0.51 - \pm 0.75$	High positive/negative correlation
$\pm 0.26 - \pm 0.50$	Moderately small positive/negative correlation
$\pm 0.01 - \pm 0.25$	Very small positive/negative correlation
0.00	No correlation

Statistical Analysis

Collected data were tallied and analyzed using descriptive statistics, particularly frequency, percentage, correlation, and weighted mean. SPSS were used to process the data and interpret the findings in alignment with the study's statement of the problem. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was used to compute the relationship between the study variables. This test was selected as it is suitable for testing linear relationships in terms of strength and direction

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Variables	Frequency	Percent	Qualitative Description
Age			
19 -23	25	83.3	Emerging Adult
24 -28	2	6.7	Early Adulthood
29 -33	2	6.7	Established young Adult
34 -38	1	3.3	Early Middle Adulthood
Total	30	100%	
Sex			
Male	4	13.33	
Female	26	86.67	
	30	100%	
Number of Hours in Watching Video			
1-3 hours	22	73.3	
3-6 hours	7	23.3	
7-10 hours	1	3.3	
	30	100.0	
Frequency of Watching Educational Video			
Less than a week	14	46.7	
3-4 times a week	7	23.3	
Daily	5	16.7	

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Rarely/Never	4	13.3	
	30	100.0	

Table 1

Age. Most of the respondents, 25 or 83.33%, were between emerging adults, while 2 respondents (6.67%) aged 24 to 28, another 2 (6.67%) aged 29 to 33, and only 1 respondent (3.33%) was in the age range of 34 to 38. This indicates that most of the respondents were youth

Sex. Out of 30 participants, 86.67 % were women while there were only 13.33% men respondents. It is then obvious that there were more female respondents than men.

Number of Hours Spent. 22 respondents or 73.33% reported spending 1 to 3 hours, followed by 7 respondents (23.33%) who spent 3 to 6 hours, and only 1 respondent (3.33%) who spent 7 to 10 hours. This suggests that most of the respondents spent a limited amount of time within the lower range of hours

Frequency of Watching Educational Video, 14 respondents or 46.67% engaged in the activity less than a week, 7 respondents (23.33%) reported doing it 3 to 4 times a week, 5 respondents (16.67%) indicated daily engagement, and 4 respondents (13.33%) said they rarely or never engaged. This implies that nearly half of the participants interacted infrequently, while only a small portion reported daily involvement.

Weighted Mean on the impact of video consumption on second language acquisition of BSED second-year English students in terms of Vocabulary Acquisition

VOCABULARY ACQUISITION	MEAN	Video Impact
1. Watching videos has helped me learn new English words effectively.	4.43	Very High Impact
2. I remember vocabulary better when I see it used in videos compared to textbooks.	4.43	Very High Impact
3. Videos expose me to diverse vocabulary not commonly found in classroom materials.	4.1	High Impact
4. I use new words learned from videos in my daily speaking or writing.	4.2	Very High Impact
5. Videos with subtitles improve my vocabulary acquisition	4.37	Very High Impact
6. Watching English videos regularly has increased my vocabulary range	4.27	Very High Impact
7. Contextual use of words in videos helps me understand their meanings better.	4.17	High Impact
8. Videos provide vocabulary relevant to real-life situations.	4.2	Very High Impact
9. I am motivated to learn vocabulary by watching interesting video content.	4.13	High Impact

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10. My vocabulary test scores have improved because of video exposure.	4.07	High Impact
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.237	Very High Impact

The data in Table 2.1 shows that video consumption has a very high impact on vocabulary acquisition among second year BSED English students at Abuyog Community College, with an overall weighted mean of 4.237. Students find video-based learning highly effective, especially for learning new words and retaining vocabulary through visual context. Top-rated factors include the use of subtitles, regular viewing, and applying new words in daily communication. While all indicators show positive effects, some—like exposure to diverse vocabulary and improved test scores—reflect slightly lower but still high impact.

Weighted Mean on the Impact of Video Consumption on Second Language Learning of English Students in Terms of Pronunciation Improvement

PRONUNCIATION IMPROVEMENT	MEAN	Video Impact
1. Watching videos helps me imitate correct English pronunciation	4.57	Very High Impact
2. I pay attention to intonation and stress patterns when listening to videos.	4.17	High Impact
3. Videos improve my confidence in speaking English aloud.	4.13	High Impact
4. Listening to native speakers in videos has improved my pronunciation accuracy	4.03	High Impact
5. Videos have helped me reduce my accent.	3.83	High Impact
6. I practice repeating phrases I hear in videos to improve pronunciation.	4.13	High Impact
7. Videos with slow and clear speech are particularly helpful for my pronunciation.	4.43	Very High Impact
8. Regular video watching helps me hear different English accents and dialects.	4.2	Very High Impact
9. Videos support my learning of correct English rhythm and intonation.	4.23	Very High Impact
10. My pronunciation feedback from teachers has improved after watching more videos.	4.13	High Impact
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.185	High Impact

Table 2.2 shows that video consumption has a high impact (overall mean = 4.185) on pronunciation improvement among second year BSED English students at Abuyog Community College. Students find videos helpful for imitating correct pronunciation, understanding rhythm and intonation, and recognizing various accents. Top-rated items include audiovisual modeling (mean = 4.57) and clear speech (mean = 4.43). While all indicators reflect positive effects, accent reduction (mean = 3.83) showed the lowest impact, suggesting it may need more focused practice.

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Weighted Mean on the Impact of Video Consumption on Language Learning in Terms of Motivation and Engagement

MOTIVATION AND ENGAGEMENT	MEAN	Video Impact
1. Videos make learning English more enjoyable and interesting for me.	4.3	Very High Impact
2. I feel more motivated to learn when I watch relevant video content.	4.3	Very High Impact
3. Videos encourage me to spend more time practicing English outside class.	4.13	High Impact
4. I am inspired to improve my English after watching educational videos.	4.33	Very High Impact
5. Video-based learning feels less stressful than traditional classroom methods.	4.07	High Impact
6. I actively participate in class discussions influenced by videos I watched.	3.87	High Impact
7. Videos encourage me to explore new aspects of English language and culture.	4.03	High Impact
8. I prefer video-supported lessons over text-only lessons.	4.07	High Impact
9. Watching videos with peers makes language learning more social and fun.	4.17	High Impact
10. Video content aligns well with my personal interests, increasing engagement.	4.13	High Impact
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.14	High Impact

Table 2.3 shows that video consumption has a high impact (mean = 4.14) on the motivation and engagement of second year BSED English students at Abuyog Community College. Students find video-based learning enjoyable, emotionally engaging, and inspiring, with top-rated items highlighting increased motivation and interest. Videos also promote self-improvement, reduce stress, and encourage social, collaborative learning outside the classroom.

CONTEXTUAL UNDERSTANDING	MEAN	Video Impact
1. Videos help me understand how to use English words and phrases in context.	4.27	Very High Impact
2. Watching videos improves my understanding of idioms and expressions.	4.13	High Impact
3. Videos expose me to cultural references that enhance language comprehension.	4.17	High Impact
4. I learn appropriate language usage for different social situations through videos.	4.1	High Impact
5. Contextual examples in videos improve my ability to interpret meaning.	4.17	High Impact
6. Watching videos helps me understand the tone and intent behind spoken English.	4.3	Very High Impact

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7. I find it easier to remember language learned in meaningful contexts from videos.	4.1	High Impact
8. Videos help me distinguish between formal and informal language use.	4.17	High Impact
9. Using video content has improved my cultural awareness in second language use.	4.27	Very High Impact
10. I feel more confident applying language skills learned from videos in real life.	4.13	High Impact
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.181	High Impact

This Table reveals that video consumption has a high impact (mean = 4.181) Videos help students grasp real-world language use, improve cultural awareness, and interpret tone and intent. High-rated items highlight benefits in understanding idioms, cultural references, and distinguishing formal from informal language, making video content a valuable tool for natural and confident English use.

Weighted Mean on the Impact of Video Consumption on Second Language Learning of BSED Second-year English Students in Terms of Listening Comprehension

LISTENING COMPREHENSION	MEAN	Description
1. Regular video watching has improved my ability to understand spoken English.	4.07	High Impact
2. I find it easier to follow conversations in English after watching videos.	4.33	Very High Impact
3. Videos with natural speech help me develop better listening skills.	4.13	High Impact
4. I understand varied English accents better due to video exposure.	4.1	High Impact
5. Video content helps me improve my ability to catch key information when listening.	4.23	Very High Impact
6. I have noticed improvement in listening test scores from video-based learning.	4.17	High Impact
7. Watching English videos prepares me for real-life listening situations.	4.17	High Impact
8. I am less likely to need repetition when listening to English after watching videos.	3.9	High Impact
9. Videos help me understand different speaking speeds better.	4.13	High Impact
10. Listening comprehension has become easier owing to video usage in my learning.	4.13	High Impact
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.136	High Impact

Table 2.5 shows that video consumption has a high impact (mean = 4.136) on the listening comprehension of second year BSED English students at Abuyog Community College. Students report improved ability to follow conversations and catch key information, with top-rated items scoring above 4.2. Videos also enhance understanding of natural speech, varied accents, and real-life

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listening scenarios. Even the lowest-rated item (mean = 3.9) reflects increased confidence, underscoring the overall effectiveness of video-based learning in developing listening skills.

Correlation Between Respondents' Profile and Video Consumption

PROFILE CHARACTERISTICS	PEARSON CORRELATION	SIG.	ADJECTIVAL INTERPRETATION
Age	-.071	.708	Very Small Positive/Negative Correlation
Sex	.347	.060	Moderate Positive Correlation
Frequency	-.382	.037	Moderate Negative Correlation
Number of Hours	.341	.065	Moderate Positive Correlation

Age. Findings shows that age was not significantly associated with the video consumption, indicated Very Small Positive/Negative Correlation ($r = -.071$, $p = .708$). This suggests that the same effects were found for students regardless of age, from video consuming.

Sex was moderately and positively correlated ($r = 0.347$) however, indicating that gender might be a differentiating factor in the way video consumption impacts students. However, the result was not statistically significant ($p = 0.060$), which would mean that the overall differences observed between male and female students were not sufficiently statistically significant to allow to establish a meaningful relationship between the variables.

Frequency. One of the findings was that there was a moderate negative correlation with video consumption for the frequency of watching educational videos ($r = -.382$, $p = .037$). This supports the view that pupils who view LCD more often are likely to have less negative or more controlled viewing effects as a result of their viewing being somewhat purposeful and potentially academically driven.

Number of Hours in Watching Educational Videos was moderately positively correlated ($r = 0.341$) and this relationship was not statistically significant ($p = 0.065$). Although the finding would suggest that viewing time of testimony is likely to be impacted by greater hours of viewing, it is impossible to draw any firm conclusion from the data available.

Proposed Intervention to Enhance English Language Learning Through Video Consumption

The researchers recommend implementing a "Structured Video-Enhanced Language Learning Program" designed to maximize the benefits of video consumption in second language acquisition. This program incorporates carefully selected educational videos into the curriculum, paired with guided activities such as vocabulary mapping, pronunciation practice, and listening comprehension exercises. To prevent the drawbacks of excessive viewing, video sessions would be limited in length and combined with reflective tasks to promote active engagement. The program also offers diverse video formats to accommodate different learning preferences, especially considering the influence of sex on motivation and pronunciation improvement. Regular exposure to short, language-rich clips would reinforce vocabulary acquisition, while teachers facilitate discussion

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and feedback to help students deepen their understanding. Overall, this approach transforms passive video watching into an interactive, learner-centered experience that enhances language proficiency while maintaining cognitive balance and inclusivity.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study highlights the complex role of video consumption in second language learning among Second Year BSED English students at Abuyog Community College. Age does not significantly affect perceived benefits, but sex and viewing habits, especially frequency and duration, impact language skills differently. Frequent video exposure improves vocabulary, while excessive viewing can hinder pronunciation, contextual understanding, and listening comprehension.

The study recommends educators use a structured approach to integrating video content, aligning videos with clear learning objectives and encouraging active engagement through tasks like vocabulary and pronunciation exercises. Regular, focused viewing is preferable to prolonged sessions, and instructional methods should accommodate individual differences, particularly sex, by offering varied and interactive content. Video use should complement broader, learner-centered teaching strategies.

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